

Elements of Theology

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Entry tags: Ancient Greek text, Greek Religions, Religious Group, Greek Philosophical Traditions, Text, Neoplatonism, Platonism

Proclus's "Elements of Theology" is the most systematic exposition of Neoplatonic metaphysics, an academic text in a systematic form that connects Greco-Roman antiquity with the Christian Middle Ages. This text, in fact, like most of the Neoplatonic writings, having influenced Christian theology mainly through the strange figure of pseudo-Denys the Aeropagite, appeared in its entirety at the beginning of the early humanist renaissance, both in Byzantium as well as in Italy, although, like other Neoplatonic texts, it survived in Arab philosophy through commentaries. Its author, Proclus of Lycia, or Proclus the Successor, was one of the most influential philosophical commentators of antiquity and is regarded as the greatest Neoplatonic philosopher of the fifth century CE. The title "Successor" was given to the head of the School of Plato in Athens and signified that Proclus was the successor of his predecessor and also the latest successor of continuous Platonic scholarship going back to Plato, the founder of the Academy in Athens. In 430 or 431 CE, probably at the age of 19 or 20 years old, Proclus sailed from Alexandria to Athens. His teacher was Plutarch of Athens, who instructed Proclus on Aristotle's "De Anima" and Plato's *Phaedo*. After Plutarch's death in 432 CE Proclus was under the guidance of Syrianus, the head of the Academy in Athens. He is also said to have been taught and initiated into Chaldaean wisdom by the fifth century Greek philosopher Asclepigenia, wife of Theagenes, and the daughter of Archiades and Plutarch of Athens. After Syrianus's death, c. 437 CE Proclus became the head of the School of Plato in Athens. Proclus was a prolific writer of ancient Greek philosophy leaving behind extensive commentaries on Plato, Aristotle, Porphyry and Plotinus, books and treatises on Neoplatonic theology, epigrams and hymns. He set forth one of the most authentic and systematic expositions of Neoplatonism and his works represent the most complete statement of Platonism. Proclus stands at the end of ancient Greek philosophy and at the beginning of the philosophy of the Middle Ages. The importance of the "Elements of Theology", and what highlights the dynamics of both its spread and influence, is not the fact that it is a mere summary form of late Greco-Roman Neoplatonism, but it is the unity of the systematic form with the transitional content, which concerns concepts that broadly establish the way of philosophical meaning-making and living that we follow to this day. The unity of the systematic form with the conceptual content is an essential parameter of this text. The concepts involved in this ground-breaking text are the result of its systematic form. It is innovative because of this unity, as the tendency of the Neoplatonism of late Greco-Roman philosophy to produce systematic forms finds here its supreme expression, which decisively influenced the entire Western philosophy. The text is divided into two main sections. The first (propositions 1 to 112) presents successively the general metaphysical "oppositions" used by Neoplatonism: the one and the many, cause and effect, immovable, self-moving, and passively mobile, the transcendence and persistence, decay and continuity, progress and return, the concepts of "causa sui" and "causatum", eternity and time, substance and thought, the whole and the part, active and passive possibility, end and infinity, being, life, and knowledge. The second section (sentences 113 to 211) explains, in the light of the above "oppositions", the relations formed in each of the three great categories of spiritual being: the Gods or entities, the minds and souls, and the relations connecting each of these categories with the lower ranks of being. As far as the influence of the text is concerned, an Arabic adaptation of it was made in the 9th century, called the "Kitāb al-Ḍāḥī fī al-khayr al-maḥḍ", which was falsely attributed to Aristotle. This work was in turn translated into Latin in the 12th century by Gerhard of Cremona under the name "Liber de causis", which became a standard part of the university curriculum in the 13th century. In Byzantium, the text was studied by Michael Psellos (11th century) and translated into Georgian by Psellos's pupil Ioanne Petritsi, who also wrote a commentary on it. A Christian refutation of the work was written by the bishop Nicolaus of Methone in the 12th century. William of Moerbeke's Latin translations of Proclus' works were not widely read in the

Middle Ages, though in the 14th century a Latin commentary on the “Elements of Theology” was written by Berthold of Moosburg. Dante (c. 1265-1321) probably drew upon the “Liber de causis” for the Neoplatonic ideas in his “Divine Comedy”.

Date Range: 412 CE - 485 CE

Region: Athens, Greece

Region tags: Eastern Mediterranean, Greece, Eastern Europe, Attica

Athens, home of the Academy of Plato.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: E. R. Dodds, Proclus: The Elements of Theology. A Revised Text with Translation, Introduction, and Commentary (2nd ed.). London: Oxford University Press, 1963. ISBN 0-19-814097-5.
- Source 2: D. Calma, ed., Neoplatonism in the Middle Ages: New Commentaries on 'Liber de Causis' and 'Elementatio Theologica'. Studia Artistarum. Vol. 42. Turnhout: Brepols, 2016. ISBN 978-2-503-55474-7. (in 2 volumes)
- Source 3: H. Boese, Elementatio Theologica. Translata a Guillelmo de Morbecca. Leuven: Leuven University Press, 1987. ISBN 9789061862444
- Source 1: Proclus' Metaphysical Elements. Translated by Johnson, Thos. Atlanta, Georgia, USA: Osceola. 1909

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://hiw.kuleuven.be/dwmc-OLD/ancientphilosophy/proclus/proclused.html>
- Source 1 Description: Editions and Translations Proclus
- Source 2 URL: <https://hiw.kuleuven.be/dwmc-OLD/ancientphilosophy/proclus/proclusbiblio.html>
- Source 2 Description: Proclus Bibliography covering the years 1990-2022
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yuY4nI3uGWU>
- Source 1 Description: Proclus' Elements of Theology: Complete Summary of all 211 Propositions
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KhwtDkLP6fk>
- Source 2 Description: 1995-10-24 NSPRS 009 - Proclus' Elements of Theology

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://archive.org/details/thomastaylor/page/n805/mode/2up>

- Source 1 Description: The Theology of Plato & Elements of Theology by Proclus. The Six Books of Proclus on the Theology of Plato (also known as Platonic Theology) with a Seventh Book written by Thomas Taylor
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.sacred-texts.com/cla/flwp/index.htm>
- Source 2 Description: Fragments of the Lost Writings of Proclus by Thomas Taylor
- Source 3 URL: http://www.goddess-athena.org/Encyclopedia/Friends/Proclus/Elements_of_Theology_x.htm
- Source 3 Description: Elements of Theology
- Source 1 URL: https://librivox.org/author/6730?primary_key=6730&search_category=author&search_page=1&search_form=get_results
- Source 1 Description: Proclus Audiobooks
- Source 2 URL: <https://archive.org/details/proclus-elements-balboa>
- Source 2 Description: Proclus: Elements of Theology by Juan and Maria Balboa
- Source 3 URL: [https://homepages.uc.edu/~martinj/History_of_Logic/Neoplatonic_Logic/Proclus%20-%20Elements%20of%20Theology%20\(Johnson\)%20English.htm](https://homepages.uc.edu/~martinj/History_of_Logic/Neoplatonic_Logic/Proclus%20-%20Elements%20of%20Theology%20(Johnson)%20English.htm)
- Source 3 Description: Proclus: Metaphysical Elements

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Written

Inked

- with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Papyrus

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

- Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

- Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: It should be noted nevertheless that parts of the text were transmitted to Western Europe and became very popular through the "Liber de Causis". This latter is a Latin translation of an Arabic work that is derived from the "Elements of Theology". The work was ascribed variously to al-Fārābī or Aristotle and it was translated into Latin by Gerard of Cremona. This text was so influential that, due to its attribution to Aristotle, was regarded by medieval philosophers as a kind of appendix to Aristotle's *Metaphysics* and very soon became a standard part of the university curriculum in the 13th century. Thomas Aquinas, however, with the help of William of Moerbeke's translation of the "Elements of Theology" made in 1268, demonstrated that the "Liber de Causis" was not a work written by Aristotle, but was actually based upon Proclus's "Elements of Theology".

Reference: Doresse, Jean. "Les Sources Du "Liber De Causis"". *Revue De L'histoire Des Religions* 13 (1956): 237-38.

Reference: Taylor, Richard Charles. "The "Liber De Causis": A Study of Medieval Neoplatonism". Ph.D. Dissertation, University of Toronto, 1982.

Reference: D'Ancona-Costa, Cristina. *Recherches Sur Le "Liber De Causis"*. Paris: Librairie Philosophique J. Vrin, 1995.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text
This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.
– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?
– No

Are there clear reformist movements?
(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)
– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?
– No

Is there material significance to the text?
– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?
– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?
– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?
– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?
– Yes

Reference: Opsomer, Jan. "Organiser La Philosophie Selon Ses Éléments. Structures Argumentatives Dans Les "éléments De Théologie"". In *Relire Les "éléments De Théologie" De Proclus. Réceptions, Interprétations Antiques Et Modernes*, edited by Gwenaëlle Aubry, Luc Brisson, Philip Clart, and Laurent Lavaud, 133-76. Paris: Hermann Philosophie, 2021.

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– No

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The text is regarded as a strictly academic and theoretical work that contains little that appears to be directed either to spiritual edification or to religious controversy. It can also be regarded as an attempt to supply to the adherents of Neoplatonism a comprehensive scheme of reality and to exhibit all of the forms of true Being as necessary consequences derived in conformity with certain universal laws from a single principle. The text is not a complete epitome of Neoplatonism. It is however a complete system of theology, in the Aristotelian sense of the term, meaning that it is a sort of handbook of metaphysics.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Vocabulary

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: Not exactly a lineage, however Proclus provides a sort of ancestry that includes all of the beings in both sensible and intelligible realm. A fundamental principle of the Platonic Philosophy which Proclus readily adopts in his work is that all things primarily proceed from, and depend on, the One, i.e. the First Cause. It necessarily follows from this principle that the One precedes the Many; or, in other words, that pure, simple being is prior to the compound or multiplied. Every being, other than the First, is to a greater or less degree a number or multitude. Every number or individual thing must in some respect participate of primal oneness – otherwise it could not exist as a whole, nor in each of its parts.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

Notes: According to Proposition VII, "Every thing productive of another is better than the nature of that which is produced." This means that something productive of another is either superior, or inferior, or equal. Hence that which is produced from this has itself either a power productive of something else, or it is entirely unprolific.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

Notes: According to Proposition XX, "The essence of soul is beyond all bodies". After all, Proclus follows the platonic axiom according to which the soul is an incorporeal essence, eternal occupant of a person's being. Plato said that even after death, the soul exists and retains the ability to think. He believed that as bodies perish, a soul is continually reborn (metempsychosis) in subsequent bodies.

Reference: Dixon, Thomas . *From Passions to Emotions: The Creation of a Secular Psychological Category*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2003.

Reference: Finamore,, John , and Emilie Kutash. "Proclus on the Psychê: World Soul and the Individual Soul". In *All from One: A Guide to Proclus*, 122–38. Oxford: Oxford Academic, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199640331.003.0006>.

Reference: Maclsaac, Gregory . "The Soul and the Virtues in Proclus' Commentary on the Republic of Plato". *Philosophie Antique* 9 (2009): 115–43. <https://doi.org/10.4000/philosant.2645>.

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– Field doesn't know

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Field doesn't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: It should be noted that the author of the text relies heavily on the Plotinian hierarchical order of beings. According to this latter, the One (or what one would call "the supreme high-God) is the absolutely simple first principle of all. It is both 'self-caused' and the cause of being for everything else in the universe. Since the One is absolutely simple, how can it be the cause of the being of anything much less the cause of everything? The One is such a cause in the sense that it is virtually everything else. This means that it stands to everything else as, for

example, white light stands to the colors of the rainbow, or the way in which a properly functioning calculator may be said to contain all the answers to the questions that can be legitimately put to it. Similarly, an omniscient simple deity may be said to know virtually all that is knowable.

Reference: Martjin, Marije, and Lloyd Gerson. "Proclus' System". In *All from One: A Guide to Proclus*, edited by Marije Martjin and Pieter d'Hoine, 45-72. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2016.

Reference: Butler, Edward P.. "The Gods and Being in Proclus". *Dionysius* 26 (2008): 93-114.

Reference: Kordig, Carl . "Proclus on the One". *Idealistic Studies* 3, no. 3 (1973): 29-237.
<https://doi.org/10.5840/idstudies19733317>.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

Notes: According to the author of the text, all that is divine has a substance which is goodness, a potency which has the character of unity, and a mode of knowledge which is secret and incomprehensible to all secondary beings alike. Divine goodness defines the substance of the Supreme High God included. Hence, even if the Supreme High God has all three major divine attributes, i.e. knowledge, potency, and goodness, yet his

substance is characterized and his proper nature determined by that which is best, namely goodness.

Reference: Steel, Carlos. "The One and the Good: Some Reflections on a Neoplatonic Identification". In *The Neoplatonic Tradition. Jewish, Christian and Islamic Themes*, edited by Arie Johan Vanderjagt and Detlev Pätzold, 9-25. Köln: Dinter, 1991.

Reference: Steel, Carlos. "The Greatest Thing to Learn Is the Good. On the Claims of Ethics and Metaphysics to Be the First Philosophy". In *Die Metaphysik Und Das Gute: Aufsätze Zu Ihrem Verhältnis in Antike Und Mittelalter: Jan A. Aertsen Zu Ehren*, edited by Wouter Goris, 1-25. Leuven: Peeters, 1999.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– No

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

Reference: Greig, Jonathan. "Proclus on the One's Causality". In *The First Principle in Late Neoplatonism. A Study of the One's Causality in Proclus and Damascius, 154-218*. *Philosophia Antiqua* 156. Leiden: Brill, 2020.
https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004439092_006.

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– No

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– No

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– Yes

Notes: Proclus in fact, composed hymns, which contain homage and praises not only of the gods adored among the Greeks, but also worshiped the god Marnas of Gaza, Asklepius Leontuchus of Ascalon, Thyandrites who is much worshipped among the Arabs, the Isis who has a temple at Philae, and indeed all other divinities. He had also witnessed the apparitions of Hecate under a luminous form.

Reference: Finamore, John. "Proclus on Ritual Practice in Neoplatonic Religious Philosophy". In *Being or Good?: Metamorphoses of Neoplatonism*, edited by Agnieszka Kijewska, 123–37. Lublin: Wydawnictwo KUL, 2004.

Reference: van den Berg, Robbert. "Theurgy in the Context of Proclus' Philosophy". In *All from One: A Guide to Proclus*, edited by Pieter d'Hoine and Marije Martjin, 223–39. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2016.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– No

Notes: For the author of the text, the Supreme High God remains hidden from any kind of knowledge and is different from all beings. Thus, the Supreme High God escapes every cognitive and every verbal effort that attempts to describe him, so that it is completely unknown and unspeakable, as it is beyond all beings. Because it has superiority over all beings, it is impossible for anyone to posit any opinion about the Supreme High God. Proclus, in fact, considered the Supreme High God as the subject of both unity and essence, confusing his attributes (e.g. his goodness) with his existence. Because the omnipresent Supreme High God has no complicity or relationship with any other being, all scientific, empirical, logical and expressive efforts are utterly meaningless; the Supreme High God, therefore, transcends understanding, remaining beyond all knowledge.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Reference: Butler, Edward. "The Intelligible Gods in the Platonic Theology of Proclus". *Méthexis* 21 (2008): 131-43.

Reference: Chlup, Radek . "Proclus' Polytheistic Theology". In *Proclus: An Introduction*, 112-36. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2012.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?
– No

↳ Organized hierarchically?
– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?
– No

↳ Other organization of pantheon?
– Specify: No other organization

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?
– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?
– No

Are other categories of beings present?
– Other [specify]: No

Does the text guide divination practices?
– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?
– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?
– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Notes: All kinds of virtue depend on the unity of beings with the One (i.e. what one would call the supreme high-God). Nothing can have an existence, unless it possesses the One by participation. Unless the One is present in every being, they will not exist. Hence, when they are divided, so far as they lose the One they change their existence. The bodies, also, of plants and animals, each of which is one, if they fly from the One, thereby becoming dissipated into multitude, will lose the essence which they before possessed, no longer being that which they were, but becoming other things, and continuing to be these so long as they are one. Health, likewise, subsists when the body is congregated into one and beauty flourishes when the nature of The One confines the parts of the body. And Virtue reigns in the soul when the soul tends to unity, and is united in one concord.

Reference: Baltzly, Dirk . "The Virtues and 'becoming Like God': Alcinous to Proclus". *Oxford Studies in Ancient Philosophy* 26 (2004): 297-321.

Reference: Chlup, Radek. "Proclus' Theory of Evil: An Ethical Perspective". *International Journal of the Platonic Tradition* 3, no. 1 (2009): 26-57. <https://doi.org/10.1163/187254708x397405>.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: However, the author of the text was a very pious man. According to his biographer, Marinus, Proclus honored gods such as Marnas and Isis, he prayed to Asklepios and Panas to achieve miraculous cures, while he was initiated in the Orphic and Chaldean doctrines.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Adherents of the Neoplatonic philosophical schools in Athens and Alexandria.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– An empire

Notes: The text was not destroyed, or even forbidden. On the contrary, it was read, however several Church officials (e.g. bishops, abbots etc) wrote refutations against the text. The most famous of these latter was that of Nicolaus, bishop of Methone in Peloponnese (early 12th century), who wrote the "Refutation (Anaptyxis) of Proclus' Elements of Theology"

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– Field doesn't know

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: As with Proclus's other works, so the "Elements of Theology" was supposed to be taught in the neoplatonic school of Athens, as well as the neoplatonic school of Alexandria.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Notes: Quite the contrary. Neoplatonism has to exhibit several women philosophers in its ranks.

Reference: Addey, Crystal. "Diotima, Sosipatra and Hypatia: Methodological Reflections on the Study of Female Philosophers in the Platonic Tradition". In *Women and the Female in Neoplatonism*, edited by Jana Schultz and James Wilberding. Leiden: Brill, n.d..

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Elements of Theology, Uzdavinys, Algis. Philosophy and Theurgy in Late Antiquity. San Raphael, CA: Angelico Press/Sophia Perennis, 2014.

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Reference: Elements of Theology, Spanu, Nicola. Proclus and the Chaldaean Oracles A Study on Proclean Exegesis, with a Translation and Commentary of Proclus' Treatise on Chaldaean Philosophy. London: Routledge, 2022.

Reference: Elements of Theology, O'Meara, Dominick. "Psellos' Commentary on the Chaldaean Oracles and Proclus' Lost Commentary". In *Platonismus Und Esoterik in Byzantischen Mittelalter Und Italienischer Renaissance*, edited by Helmut Seng, 45-58. Heidelberg: Universitätsverlag Winter, 2013.

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Reference: Elements of Theology, Zimmermann, Fritz. "Proclus Arabus Rides Again". *Arabic Sciences and Philosophy* 4, no. 1 (1994): 9-51. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0957423900001855>.

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Reference: Elements of Theology, Calma, Dragos, ed.. *Reading Proclus and the Book of Causes. On Causes and the Noetic Triad*. Edited by Dragos Calma. Vol. 3. Leiden: Brill, 2022.

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